

STUDY OF RUMI'S WORKS BY FEMALE SCHOLARS.

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ABSTRACT

Annemarie Schimmel has been one of the most sensitive Western interpreters of Rumi for many years. Her masterfully concise and highly readable book, published for the first time in English, discusses the religious and cultural foundations of Rumi's Sufism and the dominant strands of his imagery. Schimmel shows how Rumi's work, although timeless and with enduring cross-cultural appeal, must ultimately be understood as part of the larger Islamic mystical tradition, albeit as an expression of that tradition that remains unrivaled in its beauty and depth. Jalaluddin Rumi can only be described through excellence. After all, Rumi is the most famous and perhaps the greatest representative of the mystical tradition in Islam. The Masnavi, Rumi's longest and most fully realized poetic work, survives in the eastern lands of Islam. Perhaps even more surprisingly, at least for those not already familiar with his works, Rumi is also often cited as the most widely read poet in the world today. The richness of his language and his insightful spiritual understanding of the divine mean that Rumi has an enduring ability to transport readers across any culture, Islamic or otherwise.

Key words: Scholar, Rumi, Annamarie Shimmel, representative, Islam, spiritual, ability, interpreter, discuss, religious, dominant, tradition, mystical, female, divine.

A leading German Islamicist, scholar, literary figure, orientalist, an authoress of and a prolific writer more than hundred books who was well-known throughout the western world and the Islamic for her extra-ordinary talents, mystical and innovative writings and translations of Persian, Urdu, Arabic, Turkish and Sindhi works into English and German Annamarie Shimmel at last left for the world hereafter on January 28, 2003. She is widely known as an authority on Sufism. She born in Erfurt, Germany in 1922, and developed a fascination for Islam at the age of 15 and began studying the Arabic language. At the young age of 19, she obtained a Ph.D. in Islamic studies from Berlin University and pursued further studies at the University of Berlin and in Marburg, eventually becoming a professor of comparative religious studies.

Annemarie Schimmel held the position of Professor of Indo-Muslim studies at Harvard University until recently. Throughout her academic journey, she delivered lectures at universities around the globe, including Ankara, Bonn, Harvard, New York, and London. Despite remaining unmarried for 82 years, her commitment to scholarship was unwavering, making it evident that she was devoted to the pursuit of knowledge. From 1958 onwards, she frequently traveled to Pakistan to lecture, particularly focusing on Iqbal. Over time, Pakistan became like a second home to her. She made several visits to the shrines of Sindh, fulfilling her spiritual curiosity, and expressed a deep admiration for Iqbal, who had always been her cherished poet, guiding her from the beginning. When discussing his poetry, she would passionately speak for hours, captivating her audience and often closing her eyes in sheer delight and inspiration while reciting his verses, immersing herself in profound imagination akin to a true poet. She approached translating Iqbal's poetry with a fervent spiritual dedication. Her translation of Allama Iqbal's *Payam-i-Mashriq*, titled *Botschaft des Ostens*, stands as a significant achievement in the German language. Additionally, her German translations of *Javed Nama* and *Bang-i-Dara*, known as *Dschavidnma Das Buch* and *Der Ewigkeit* respectively, alongside her scholarly work *Gabraeil's Wing: A Study of the Religious Ideas of Sir Mohammad Iqbal*, are highly respected contributions to the study of Iqbal in English-speaking academia. Furthermore, she delivered outstanding lectures on Iqbal at the prestigious South Asia Institute at Heidelberg University. For many years, she consistently honored Iqbal Day in Pakistan and if ever she missed the celebration due to prior commitments, she would mark the occasion at the Heidelberg Town Hall or another location, setting aside all other responsibilities. Alongside her dedication to studying Iqbal, she also immersed herself in exploring the teachings of the spiritual mentor Maulana Rumi, whose growing popularity in the Western world owes much to her significant contributions. Her book, *Triumphal Sun: A Study of the Works of Jalaluddin Rumi*, published in London in 1978, serves as a remarkable homage to Rumi. In her comprehensive work, *Through a Veil Mystical Poetry in Islam*, she delves into the evolution of Islamic mystical poetry, delving into the works of individual Sufi poets like the renowned Rumi and exploring topics such as sacred verse and enigmatic and nonsensical poetry. This book offers an insightful and captivating exploration of some of the most exquisite literature in existence. In her publication *My Road to Sufism*, Dr. Schimmel recounts her journey of becoming fascinated with Sufism. Another significant contribution is her book *Mystical Dimensions of Islam*,

published by Chapel Hill in 1975, which further solidified her reputation as an authority on Rumi and Sufism. Annemarie Schimmel has been one of the most sensitive Western interpreters of Rumi for many years. Her masterfully concise and highly readable book, published for the first time in English, discusses the religious and cultural foundations of Rumi's Sufism and the dominant strands of his imagery. Schimmel shows how Rumi's work, although timeless and with enduring cross-cultural appeal, must ultimately be understood as part of the larger Islamic mystical tradition, albeit as an expression of that tradition that remains unrivaled in its beauty and depth. Jalaluddin Rumi can only be described through excellence. After all, Rumi is the most famous and perhaps the greatest representative of the mystical tradition in Islam. The Masnavi, Rumi's longest and most fully realized poetic work, survives in the eastern lands of Islam. Perhaps even more surprisingly, at least for those not already familiar with his works, Rumi is also often cited as the most widely read poet in the world today. The richness of his language and his insightful spiritual understanding of the divine mean that Rumi has an enduring ability to transport readers across any culture, Islamic or otherwise.

Annemarie Schimmel discusses the following issues in her research called "Shams Shukuhi": 1) ancient history and adventure book; 2) Rumi's world of imagination; 3) Rumi's theology: the relationship between the Creator and created beings, Rumi's views on man; 4) Comments of Persian-speaking writers and scientists about Rumi's work; 5) Memoirs of the author. This book was translated into Persian by Hasan Lohuti and published in Tehran in 1989. In this work, Annemarie Schimmel explores Mawlavi's thoughts on mysticism and theology. She pays serious attention to philosophical thoughts on topics such as revelation, the status of man, the reflection of the material world, and the true root of true love. Annemarie Schimmel's research on the influence of Maulana Jalaluddin Rumi on German poets and writers in the period of 19th century romanticism is a rare phenomenon in the field of science. She translated Mawlavi's "Fihi mo fihi" into English. In addition, Schimmel wrote many articles on Mawlavi's teachings. In 1948, A. Schimmel published a deep and extensive scientific study of the images and images in "Masnavi" in German. This book is the result of the scholar's many years of research on Rumi's creative activity.

The author of The Essential Rumi, Coleman Barks, wrote the followings about Schimmel: "Annemarie Schimmel has been immersed in Rumi for over forty years. Her scholarship and devotion are magnificent. She has a deep

understanding of the poems, the mystical puns, the music, and the dancy inner meanings of Rumi's work."

Ms. Schimmel has created more than 120 works on topics related to Islam and Sufism in general. The scientist was awarded with the highest awards of many countries, including Uzbekistan. "Beloved in my soul" is one of the most beautiful works of Mrs. Annemarie Schimmel.

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